

Human resource measurement and reporting in manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka

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Purpose- To explore and compare current practice of the measurement and reporting of human resource information by firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and 30 firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors responded. For the data analysis descriptive statistics, chi-square test, principle component factor analysis and independent sample t-test were used.

Findings- There were sectoral differences in reporting some of the human resource indicators. Human resource indicators were mainly collated internally and a limited number of indicators were externally disclosed. A majority of firms, irrespective of the business sector, maintained records of human resource indicators in the manual form. Three main factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of human resource were identified as “Insufficient resource allocation”, “Lack of knowledge in human resource measurement and reporting”, and “Negative impact on organization”.

Research limitations/implications- The research was conducted using survey research methodology as a pilot study to establish baseline data and to be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research.

Practical implications- The findings suggested that firms need to have more effective systems in the measurement and reporting of human resource.

Originality/value- The majority of past studies on the measurement and reporting of human resource were conducted on the voluntary disclosure of information in annual reports, firms were selected on the basis of the market capitalization, and data were analysed using content analysis. Yet, the literature suggests that the content analysis of disclosed annual report information is mainly based on a non-random sample of firms and many firms do not disclose all the available information. The current empirical survey-based study explored and compared human resource measurement and reporting practices of firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: human resource, human resource measurement, human resource reporting, disclosure, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

Human resource is one of the key resources of an organization that is occupying a position of increasing importance in the current business environment. The literature identifies human resource (HR) as a primary driver in creating firm value (O'Donnell and Berkery, 2003; O'Regan et al. 2001; Wright and Snell 2005; Youndt et al., 1996). Hence, there is an increasing interest in the measurement, management and reporting of this key resource (Ax and Marton, 2008; Chaudhry and Roomi, 2010; Verma and Dewe, 2008). For instance, Verma and Dewe (2008) suggested that managing, measuring and reporting of HR provide needed information about the people resources in the organisation and if the people resources are there to support business strategies.

The current study explores HR measurement and reporting practices of firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka. The current study is different from previous studies in several respects. First, the majority of past studies on the measurement and reporting of HR were conducted on the voluntary disclosure of information in annual reports, firms were selected on the basis of the market capitalization, and data were analysed using content analysis (e.g. Abeysekera, 2008; Abeysekera and Guthrie, 2004; Guthrie and Petty, 2000; Kamath, 2008; Nurunnabi et al., 2011; Olsson, 2001). Yet, literature suggests two main issues in connection to content analysis, i.e., the content analysis of disclosed annual report information is mainly based on a non-random sample of firms (Ax and Marton, 2008) and many firms do not disclose all the available information (Ax and Marton, 2008; Khan and Ali, 2010; Khan and Khan, 2010).

Second, the literature suggests the importance of human resource management (HRM) practices of acquisition, development, allocation, replacement or retention of employees and reporting of HR information (Flamholtz, 1972). In this regard, Abhayawansa and Abeysekera (2008) highlighted the importance of investigating HRM practices and organisational systems that are in place to leverage the value of HR. Some past studies suggests that firms may be motivated to voluntary disclose information under certain conditions (such as a need to portray a positive image). For instance, the U.K. government's

initiative in accounting for people (Department of Trade and Industry, 2003), and its associated consultation work by Foong et al. (2003) revealed that even publicly listed companies do not disclose externally most of the HR related information. In this regard, Samudhram et al. (2010) argue that voluntary reporting does not occur when motivating forces are absent; if organizations do not publish pertinent information, it is not possible to study based on published material since no published material is available for the initial exploration. However, very limited number of studies were conducted to provide real-life scenario (e.g. Beattie and Smith, 2010; Department of Trade and Industry, 2003; Foong et al., 2003; PricewaterhouseCoopers, n.d.; Verma and Dewe, 2004). In such studies, Beattie and Smith (2010) and Boedker et al. (2004) reveal that marked differences exist between the extent to which HR information is internally collated and externally disclosed, where the communication to external stakeholders of HR information appears to be deficient.

Third, the literature suggests the importance of human capital management practices for firms' competitive advantage. In this regard, on the one hand, some scholars suggest that HR is a critical factor to the service-based sector than any other sector of a country (e.g. Stittle, 2004). For instance, Stittle (2004) argued that in the service sector, the assets of firms become less tangible and increased attention has to be focused upon HRM. On the other hand, some other scholars suggest the equal importance of HR to all sectors (e.g. Foong et al., 2003; Verma and Dewe, 2004). For instance, Foong et al. (2003) state that knowledge is a key differentiator in the provision of services such as consulting, investment banking and IT services but knowledge is also increasingly important in high-value-added manufacturing-based businesses such as pharmaceuticals, consumer electronics and electrical machinery. In this regard, several past studies highlighted the importance of comparing HR managing, measuring and reporting practices across business sectors (e.g. Khan and Ali, 2010; Murthy and Abeysekera, 2007). Yet, our extensive review of literature on HR measurement and reporting practices failed to find empirical studies that compared these practices between manufacturing and service sectors.

In the above context, the current survey-based study was conducted to explore and compare current practices of measurement and reporting of HR information by firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka. The specific objectives of the study are to explore and compare a) HR indicators internally collated by the firms, b) HR indicators externally disclosed by the firms, c) mechanisms used to report HR indicators, d) methods used to maintain records on HR indicators, e) persons involved in the measurement and reporting of HR indicators, and f) factors that inhibit effective measurement and reporting of HR of the two business sectors. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand HR measurement and reporting in Sri Lanka. By doing so, this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

The American Accounting Association defined HR reporting as the process of identifying and measuring data about HR and communicating this information to interested parties; its purpose is to improve the quality of financial decisions made by parties (1973, p. 169). Hence, information provided by HR reporting can be used to deepen the understanding of cost and value of HR and can be used to guide HR decision making. With regard to the terminology used, the majority of past studies used the term “human capital” (e.g. Abeysekera and Guthrie, 2004; Foong et al., 2003), some studies used the term “employees” (e.g. Bukh et al., 2005) while some other studies used the term “human resource” (e.g. Verma and Dewe, 2008). To suit the context of the current study, we also use the term “human resource”.

Human resource indicators

Past studies have categorised HR indicators into several broad areas (Abeysekera, 2008; Foong et al., 2003; Marr et al., 2003). For instance, Foong et al. (2003) categorized these into eight broad areas, namely, turnover/retention/absence, competencies/training,

employee productivity, workforce profile, employee attitude/engagement, employee compensation, recruitment, and health and safety. Marr et al. (2003) categorized these into four broad areas, namely demographics, competence, attitude, and HRM practices (such as training expenses, recruitment practices, etc). Abeysekera (2008) categorized these into seven broad areas, namely, training and development, entrepreneurial skills, equity issues, employee safety, employee relations, employee welfare, and employee-related measurements. However, it should be noted that there are no common measures of HR even within a particular country and this makes comparisons between countries difficult (Foong et al., 2003).

Internal collation of HR indicators. Firms internally collate and externally disclose certain HR indicators with the strategic intent of recruiting, developing and retaining key talent (PricewaterhouseCoopers, n.d.). However, previous studies suggest that there are deficiencies in both internal collation and external disclosure of HR information (Beattie and Smith, 2010; Verma and Dewe, 2004).

With regard to internal collation of HR indicators, Beattie and Smith (2010) found that indicators on employee turnover, employee training and development, and workplace safety were frequently internally collated while indicators on employee entrepreneurial skills, employee adaptability, and employee reputation were not frequently internally collated. This may be due to the lack of precision of measures (Verma and Dewe, 2004). According to Verma and Dewe (2004), the lack of precision of measures would apply to more subjective indicators such as “employee entrepreneurial skills”, “employee adaptability”, and “employee reputation”, each of which was internally collated by very limited number of firms in their study.

Based on the literature reviewed on internal collation of HR indicators (such as Abeysekera, 2008; Foong et al., 2003; Marr et al., 2003) and the literature reviewed earlier on possible differences between manufacturing and service sectors in their emphasis on HR

(such as Foong et al., 2003; Stittle, 2004; Verma and Dewe, 2004), following hypothesis was developed for the study:

Hypothesis 1: There are significant differences in the internal collation of HR indicators between manufacturing and service sectors.

External disclosure of HR indicators. With regard to external disclosure of HR indicators, Beattie and Smith (2010) identified that the most frequently externally disclosed HR indicators were workplace safety and employee remuneration. According to PricewaterhouseCoopers (n.d.), the most frequently externally disclosed HR indicators were workforce demographics, remuneration, and basic measures such as absenteeism rates. According to Verma and Dewe (2004), the most frequently externally disclosed HR indicators were absenteeism, turnover rates, competencies, training and educational costs. According to Murthy and Abeysekera (2007), the most frequently externally disclosed HR indicators were employee featured, employee thanked, training, education and know-how, employee involvement in community, and employee numbers. These findings suggest that there is no consensus on the disclosure of HR indicators.

With regard to external disclosure and management of HR information, Murthy and Abeysekera (2007) found that some HR practices were least-disclosed but efficiently managed (such as employee safety, equity issues based on gender, race, and religion), some other HR practices were least-disclosed and inefficiently managed (such as equity issues based on disability), while some other HR practices were least-disclosed and not managed at all (such as union activity).

In this regard, mandatory disclosures compel firms to disclose information in the corporate annual report, and it is up to the discretion of firms to disclose information beyond these mandatory requirements. However, the literature suggests that there are lack of mandatory requirements in the measurement and reporting of HR, and as a consequence, majority of listed companies do not disclose many of their HR indicators in annual reports (Beattie and Smith, 2010; Foong et al., 2003; Stittle, 2004; Verma and Dewe, 2008). For

instance, Beattie and Smith (2010) and PricewaterhouseCoopers (n.d.) state that firms disclose HR indicators such as workforce demographics, remuneration, and absenteeism rates in order to comply with local legislation or financial control. Hence, several previous studies found differences in internal collation and external disclosure of HR indicators, where there are deficiencies in the disclosure of HR indicators to external stakeholders (Beattie and Smith, 2010; Boedker et al., 2004; PricewaterhouseCoopers, n.d.).

Based on the literature reviewed above on external disclosure of HR indicators (such as Beattie and Smith, 2010; PricewaterhouseCoopers, n.d.; Verma and Dewe, 2008) and the literature reviewed earlier on possible differences between manufacturing and service sectors in their emphasis on HR (such as Foong et al., 2003; Stittle, 2004; Verma and Dewe, 2004), following hypothesis was developed for the study (also refer to the section on *measures*):

Hypothesis 2: There are significant differences in external disclosure of HR indicators between manufacturing and service sectors.

Factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of human resource

Several studies identified factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR (Foong et al., 2003; Johanson, 1999; Verma and Dewe, 2004, 2008). For instance, according to Foong et al. (2003), the factors that inhibit HR measurement and reporting were HR measurement is not the first priority of the company, the lack of time and resources, the lack of awareness among HRM practitioners about the value of HR reporting, the lack of support from senior management, and the lack of clear guidance and universal practice. Foong et al. (2003) and Beattie and Smith (2010) also identified the most rated inhibiting factor in the external disclosure of HR indicators as “companies’ belief that giving away HR information may harm the competitive position”.

According to Verma and Dewe (2004, 2008) factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR were the lack of understanding of measures by others in the organisation,

uncertainty as to what information should be reported, the lack of precision in current HR measures, the lack of wide acceptance of current HR measures, the lack of reliability of current HR measures, insufficient resources available to measure HR, and the lack of time to develop appropriate HR measures. According to Johanson (1999), factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR were the lack of knowledge of HR indicators, the lack of knowledge of HR costing and accounting models, insufficient information systems to produce HR costing and accounting information, the lack of top management demand for HR costing and accounting, and the lack of time.

After an extensive review of literature on HR measurement and reporting, Stiles and Kulvisaechana (n.d. p. 20-21) categorized the factors that inhibit HR reporting into three main categories. These are “the fear of competitors”, “the fear of unions or employees”, and “a concern for practical difficulties of collecting HR information for reporting and whether investors will understand it anyway”.

On the basis of the literature reviewed above and preliminary investigations made by us in Sri Lanka, following hypothesis was developed for the study:

Hypothesis 3: There are significant differences in factors that inhibit measurement and reporting of HR between manufacturing and service sectors.

Methodology

Sample

In selecting the sample, we decided to concentrate on the best performing firms in the manufacturing and service sectors of the country. A sample of best performing private sector firms belonging to the two sectors was identified based on the criteria such as revenue growth, return on assets, the growth of market share, net profits, and profit to revenue ratio. Of the 38 firms initially contacted, 30 firms agreed to participate in the survey. Hence, the study collected data on HR measurement and reporting practices of 30 firms. Of these firms,

13 belong to manufacturing sector and 17 belong to service sector. The responded manufacturing sector firms belong to food and beverages, fast moving consumer goods, export-based wearing apparel, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, and plastic and rubber manufacturing while responded service sector firms belong to commercial banking, finance, insurance, telecommunication, and business process outsourcing.

To fulfil the expectations of this study, it was decided to collect data from the main person in charge of HR measurement and reporting in each firm. Although this method of data collection has a limitation, in the absence of reliable research evidence, obtaining information from a subject matter expert is considered a good starting point. Therefore, 15 HR managers, 8 finance directors and 7 CEOs/Directors (15+8+7=30) responded to the survey questionnaire. When considering the education level of the respondents, all the respondents had either Bachelor's degree or a postgraduate degree as the highest level of education.

Measures and methods of data analysis

There were six questions in the survey questionnaire. In the first question respondents were asked to indicate HR measures internally collated by the firms. A list of 20 HR indicators was provided. These 20 indicators were broadly classified into six categories of workforce profile, competencies and training, employee compensation, absenteeism and employee turnover, employee productivity and performance, and HR investment (refer to Table 1). Respondents rated each of the 20 items on a scale of yes (1) or no (0). This 20-item list was developed based on the studies of Foong et al. (2003), PricewaterhouseCoopers (n.d.) Verma and Dewe (2004 and 2008), Abeysekera and Guthrie (2004) and Abeysekera (2008).

The second question inquired into HR indicators that are externally disclosed by the firms. For this, the same 20-item list of HR indicators was used. Respondents rated each of the 20 items on a scale of disclosed/compulsory by the firm (1) or not disclosed/not compulsory by the firm (0).

The third question inquired into mechanisms used by the firms to report HR indicators. For this, the same 20-item list of HR indicators was used. Respondents rated each of the 20 items on a scale of 1 = HR score card to main board, 2 = HR score card within HR, 3 = Reports to HR director/manager, 4 = Special reports to external stakeholders, 5 = Special reports to line management, 6 = Special reports to employees, 7 = Separate corporate responsibility report, and 8 = Keep records and do not report to any. This scale has been used in prior research by PricewaterhouseCoopers (n.d.).

The fourth question inquired into methods used to maintain records on HR indicators. For this, the same 20-item list of HR indicators was used. Respondents rated each of the 20 items on a scale of 1 = Manual, 2 = Both manual and computerized systems, 3 = Partially manual and partially computerized system, and 4 = Fully computerized system.

The fifth question inquired into persons involved in the measurement and reporting of HR. Respondents identified the departments/persons (such as HR department) that are involved in the measurement and reporting of HR in their firms.

The last question inquired into factors that inhibit effective measurement and reporting of HR. A list of nine items was developed for the study based on the prior studies of Foong et al. (2003), Verma and Dewe (2004 and 2008), Johanson (1999), and Beattie and Smith (2010). These nine items were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

For the data analysis descriptive statistics, chi-square test, factor analysis and independent sample t-test were used. The chi-square test was used to investigate differences in HR reporting practices between manufacturing and service sectors. In the attempt to identify the underlying factors that inhibit effective measurement and reporting of HR, the nine items were subjected to exploratory factor analysis (Varimax rotation). The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. Independent

sample t-test was used to investigate differences in reasons that inhibit effective measurement and reporting of HR between manufacturing and service sectors.

Results and discussion

Human resource indicators

Table 1 shows results relating to the internal collation of HR indicators. As can be seen in Table 1, of the total sample, 53 per cent of the firms report workforce split by age. When considering the results in terms of sector, 53 per cent of the firms belonging to the manufacturing sector report workforce split by age where as 50 per cent of the firms belonging to the service sector report workforce split by age. Chi-square statistic was used to identify whether there are any sector differences in the internal collation of HR indicators. As can be seen in Table 1, of these 20 items, four items show significant differences. These are split by gender, training budget, the track of training expenditure against the budget, and employee productivity. The results of cross-tabulation revealed that service sector falls behind in reporting split by gender and employee productivity while manufacturing sector falls behind in reporting training budget and the track of training expenditure against the budget (results of cross-tabulations are not shown). Therefore, H1 is partially supported by the data.

Take in Table 1 here

Table 2 shows results relating to the external disclosure of HR indicators due to any mandatory requirement of the firm. As can be seen in Table 2, of the total sample, 16 per cent of the firms revealed that it is compulsory in their firms to report workforce split by age. When considering the results in terms of sector, 15 per cent of the firms belonging to the manufacturing sector revealed that it is compulsory in their firms to report workforce split by age where as 17 per cent of the firms belonging to the service sector revealed that it is compulsory in their firms to report workforce split by age. Chi-square statistic was used to

identify whether there are any sector differences. As can be seen in Table 1, of these 20 items two items show significant differences. These are split by gender and employee productivity. The results of cross-tabulation revealed that service sector falls behind in disclosing split by gender and employee productivity (results of cross-tabulations are not shown). Therefore, H2 is partially supported by the data.

Take in Table 2 here

Persons involved in the measurement and reporting of human resource

Table 3 shows the results relating to persons involved in the measurement and reporting of HR. As can be seen in Table 3, the HR department involved in the measurement and reporting of HR in majority of the firms followed by the finance department.

Take in Table 3 here

Mechanisms used to report human resource indicators

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse mechanisms used to report HR indicators. The summary of results relating to mechanisms mainly used for HR reporting by sector is provided in Table 4. For instance, both manufacturing and service sectors mainly keep records of race or ethnic origin of employees but this information is not reported to any stakeholders. Further, manufacturing sector mainly report information about training undergone by individual employees to HR director/manager while service sector mainly report this information to line management.

Take in Table 4 here

Methods used to maintain records on human resource indicators

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse methods used to maintain HR records by sector. The summary of results relating to methods mainly used to maintain records by each sector is provided in Table 5. For instance, both manufacturing and service sectors mainly use manual methods to maintain the records of competencies and training. Further, manufacturing sector mainly record remuneration information by using both manual and computerized systems while service sector mainly record this information by using fully computerised systems.

Take in Table 5 here

Factors that inhibit effective measurement and reporting of human resource

The study investigated nine aspects that could influence the measurement and reporting of HR. The nine-item measure had Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.888. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 74 per cent (73.99) of the variance. Of these three factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Insufficient resource allocation", Factor 2 was labelled as "Lack of knowledge in HR measurement and reporting", and Factor 3 as "Negative impact on organization". Table 6 summarizes the results of factor analysis. Two separate factor analyses for each sector were not conducted as the sample size of this study is limited to 30 firms.

Take in Table 6 here

To identify differences in the factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR, independent sample t-test was used. The results are shown in Table 7. As can be seen in Table 7, of these nine items, four items show significant differences. The items "There is no

return seen on the investment and effort required in the reporting of HR” and “There is no clear guidance in measuring and reporting HR” were highly rated by service sector firms while the items “HR information could be negatively interpreted by external stakeholders” and “HR information could be too sensitive to report” were highly rated by manufacturing sector firms. The differences in the perceptions for these four items are significant between the two sectors. Therefore, H3 is partially supported by the data.

Take in Table 7 here

Conclusions and implications

The main intention of the study was to explore and compare the current practice of measurement and reporting of HR information by firms belonging to the manufacturing and service sectors in Sri Lanka.

It was found that absenteeism, remuneration, training budget, and employee split by function were the most internally collated indicators by manufacturing sector firms while training budget, track of training expenditure against budget, absenteeism, remuneration, and employee performance were the most internally collated indicators by service sector firms. Employee split by race or ethnic origin, and HR return on investment were the least internally collated indicators by the two sectors. Further, there were sectoral differences in the internal collation of HR indicators of split by gender, training budget, the track of training expenditure against the budget, and employee productivity. It was further found that services sector falls behind in internally collating split by gender and employee productivity while manufacturing sector falls behind in internally collating training budget and the track of training expenditure against the budget. It is also apparent that manufacturing sector firms relied more on employee productivity data while service sector firms relied more on employee performance data. This situation was also observed by Foong et al. (2003).

It was also found that firms in both sectors identified the requirement of externally disclosing remuneration information. In addition to this, firms belonging to the manufacturing sector also identified the need of externally disclosing employee productivity and employee split by gender while firms belonging to the service sector identified the need of externally disclosing employee qualifications. There are significant differences between firms of the two sectors in externally disclosing employee productivity and employee split by gender. However, other than employee remuneration, which firms mainly disclose as an integral part of financial control, there are lack of requirements to measure and report HR. As suggested by Nurunnabi et al. (2011) HR measurement and reporting seem to depend on the self-interest of the firms.

The findings revealed that HRM departments mainly engaged in the measurement and reporting of HR in most of the firms followed by finance department. In some firms, system analysts were also engaged in this activity. The involvement of line managers and divisional managers in the measurement and reporting of HR is minimal. Verma and Dewe (2008) also identified the importance of HR function driving the practice of measuring and reporting HR as this function has the knowledge, expertise and data to do so. They, further, stated that if the HRM function did not involve in the valuation of HR, there may be a threat to the HRM function and a danger that other functions such as accounting would perhaps “take over” (p. 110). Yet, according to Verma and Dewe (2004), the measurement of HR is least important at the financial and management accounting function. However, the findings of our study revealed that finance department is considerably involved in this activity in Sri Lanka.

One of the objectives of the study was to explore mechanisms used by the firms to report HR. It was found that firms use eight mechanisms depending on the items to be reported, namely, HR score card to main board, HR score card within HR, reports to HR director/manager, special reports to external stakeholders, special reports to line management, special reports to employees, separate corporate responsibility report, and keep records and do not report to any stakeholders. Firms belonging to the manufacturing

sector mainly use reports to HR director/manager, HR score card within HR, and special reports to line management. Firms belonging to the service sector mainly use special reports to line management. Such mechanisms could be identified as means used by the firms to internally collate information. The usage of mechanisms to externally disclose HR information such as special reports to external stakeholders and separate corporate responsibility report were minimal by the firms belonging to both sectors. Firms belonging to both sectors revealed that indicators related to employee split by race or ethnic origin, career record, split by age, and qualifications were mainly internally collated, keep records and do not report to any party.

With regard to methods used to maintain records on HR indicators, majority of firms belong to manufacturing and service sectors revealed that they maintain records of most indicators in the manual form. majority of firms belong to manufacturing sector revealed having fully computerised systems mainly for remuneration. In this regard, Foong et al. (2003) suggest the importance of having sophisticated computerised systems to track productivity of employees and complement this information with other indicators to address morale, training and relocation issues.

With regard to factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR, the items of “no return seen on the investment and effort required in the reporting of HR” and “no clear guidance in measuring and reporting HR” were highly rated by service sector firms while the items of “HR information could be negatively interpreted by external stakeholders” and “HR information could be too sensitive to report” were highly rated by manufacturing sector firms. Significant differences were indentified between the sectors for these four items. When considering the total mean values obtained by the items that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR, the items of “organization does not allocate sufficient resources to measure and report HR”, and “HR department deals mostly with day-to-day administrative matters” were highly rated. The factor analysis revealed three underlying factors, namely, “Insufficient resource allocation”, “Lack of knowledge in HR measurement and reporting”, and “Negative impact on organization”. These factors were also identified by prior studies of Foong et al.

(2003), Verma and Dewe (2004, 2008), and Beattie and Smith (2010) as important factors that inhibit the measurement and reporting of HR.

The findings of the study have both theoretical and practical implications. First, both academics and practitioners need valid information to better understand the status of the measurement and reporting of HR. This becomes important because the importance of the measurement and reporting of HR is growing while empirical research in this area is presently lacking. Therefore, considerable future research is necessary to replicate, extend, or contradict the results presented in this article. Yet, we believe that the findings of this study provide baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Second, the extent of capturing of HR information was limited and the majority of this information was mainly collated internally; most of the HR indicators were measured and reported by the firms voluntarily. Firms mostly internally collated soft-end HR indicators such as workforce profile that can easily be extracted from secondary data. Firms least internally collated hard-end HR indicators such as HR return on investment. However, the findings imply that there is little consensus among the firms irrespective of the business sector as to what should actually be measured, why those should be measured, and how those indicators contribute to the strategic direction of the organization, and as a consequence, many HR indicators have been omitted as a resource by many firms.

Third, in connection to the above, it was also found that HRM departments mainly engaged in the measurement and reporting of HR. Hence, to effectively drive the practice of measuring and reporting HR, HRM practitioners may have to improve their knowledge and skills on the subject matter. However, changes in knowledge are not sufficient to bring about changes in habits in the measurement and reporting of HR but also an ambivalent support and commitment from top management are vital in this regard.

Fourth, when mandatory disclosure is minimal, firms have the freedom to determine HR information to be internally collated and externally disclose. The findings implied that firms reluctant to disclose most of the HR indicators to stakeholders. In many cases,

important information, such as employee career record and qualifications, was not even used for internal decision making, just kept within the firms as records. Firms do not use such information internally for management decision making nor do they disclose the information to manage relationship with external stakeholders. Such firms have ignored the fact that the effective measurement and reporting of HR has a positive impact on competitiveness and profitability of the firms. When firms reluctant to voluntarily disclose HR information, legislators should develop directives to disclose HR information within legally permitted formats.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

First, the study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology; the study relied on self-reported data. Due to the small scale of this study, we have not differentiated firms based on size of the firm in terms of either employee numbers or total assets. Future research studies could expand HR indicators by including other areas such as recruitment and employee attitudes. Further, future research with larger samples could complement questionnaire survey with interviews and secondary data. Such studies will be able to obtain a deeper and richer understanding in this area.

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Table 1: Internal collation of human resource indicators

	Total (%)	Sector (%)		P value
		Manufacturing	Service	
Workforce profile				
Split by age	53	53	50	.654
Split by gender	60	60	44	.033*
Split by race or ethnic origin	13	13	17	.462
Split by function	90	90	82	.110
Competencies and training				
Qualifications	48	48	44	.605
Career record	39	39	39	.981
Training undergone	58	58	56	.739
Identify training needs of individual employees	90	90	94	.361
Training budget	81	81	100	.001**
Track of training expenditure against the budget	81	81	94	.022*
Training undergone by individual employees	71	71	78	.326
Effectiveness of Training	42	42	44	.739
HR score card on training	31	31	41	.160
Employee compensation				
Remuneration	90	98	99	.713
Salary structure	84	84	83	.924
Absenteeism and employee turnover				
Absenteeism	93	93	88	.201
Employee turnover rates	74	74	61	.055
Employee productivity and performance				
Employee productivity	52	52	33	.011*
Employee performance	77	77	89	.164
HR investment				
HR return on investment	29	29	28	.856

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01

Table 2: External disclosure of human resource indicators

	Total (%)	Sector (%)		P value
		Manufacturing	Service	
Workforce profile				
Split by age	16	15	17	.924
Split by gender	29	54	11	.010*
Split by race or ethnic origin	3	8	0	.232
Split by function	16	31	6	.060
Competencies and training				
Qualifications	38	31	44	.440
Career record	10	15	6	.361
Training undergone	13	15	11	.726
Identify training needs of individual employees	10	15	6	.363
Training budget	7	15	0	.085
Track of training expenditure against the budget	7	15	0	.085
Training undergone by individual employees	7	15	0	.085
Effectiveness of Training	3	8	6	.234
HR score card on training	3	0	6	.388
Employee compensation				
Remuneration	97	98	96	.687
Salary structure	36	15	6	.361
Absenteeism and employee turnover				
Absenteeism	19	15	22	.634
Employee turnover rates	10	15	6	.361
Employee productivity and performance				
Employee productivity	10	69	11	.001**
Employee performance	13	23	6	.151
HR investment				
HR return on investment	7	8	6	.811

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01

Table 3: Persons involved in the measurement and reporting of human resource †

	Total (%)	Sector	
		Manufacturing (%)	Service (%)
Human resource department	90	85	94
Finance department	45	39	50
System analyst	13	15	11
Line management	3	7	5
Divisional management	3	6	4

Note: †Do not add up to 100 due to multiple answers

Table 4: Mechanisms used for reporting - mostly rated

Rank	HR score card to main board	HR score card within HR	Report to HR director/manager	Special reports to external stakeholders	Special reports to line management	Special reports to employees	Separate corporate responsibility report	Keep records and do not report to any
Manufacturing								
1	Absenteeism	Remuneration	Employee turnover rates	Remuneration	Absenteeism	Absenteeism	Training undergone	Split by race or ethnic origin
2	Employee turnover rates	Salary structure	Absenteeism	-	Identify training needs of individual employees	Employee turnover rates	-	Qualifications
3	-	Absenteeism	Salary structure	-	Remuneration	Employee productivity	-	Career record
4	-	Split by function	Training undergone by individual employees	-	Salary structure	-	-	Split by age
5	-	Employee productivity	Employee performance	-	Employee productivity	-	-	-
6		Employee turnover rates	Training undergone		Split by function			
7		Split by gender	Identify training needs of individual employees		Employee turnover rates			
8			Split by function		Employee performance			
Service								
1	-	Remuneration	Employee turnover rates		Absenteeism	Employee performance	-	Split by race or ethnic origin
2	-	Salary structure	Salary structure	-	Identify training needs of individual employees	-	-	Split by age
3	-	Split by function	-	-	Split by function	-	-	Split by gender
4	-	Absenteeism	-	-	Salary structure	-	-	Qualifications
5	-	-	-	-	Training budget	-	-	Career record
6	-	-	-	-	Track of training expenditure against the budget	-	-	-
7	-	-	-	-	Training undergone by individual employees	-	-	-
8	-	-	-	-	Employee performance	-	-	-

Note: Rank is based on percentages

All the items that are rated by more than 40 per cent are reported in this Table.

Table 5: Methods used to maintain records - mostly rated

Rank	Manual	Partially manual and partially computerized system	Fully computerized system	Both manual and computerized systems
Manufacturing				
1	HR score card on training	Absenteeism	Remuneration	Remuneration
2	Split by race or ethnic origin	Salary structure	-	Identify training needs of individual employees
3	HR return on investment	Split by function	-	Training undergone by individual employees
4	Effectiveness of Training	Employee turnover rates	-	-
5	Employee productivity	-	-	-
6	Career record	-	-	-
7	Qualifications	-	-	-
8	Training undergone	-	-	-
9	Identify training needs of individual employees	-	-	-
10	Training budget	-	-	-
11	Training undergone by individual employees	-	-	-
12	Track of training expenditure against the budget	-	-	-
13	Split by age	-	-	-
14	Employee performance	-	-	-
Service				
1	Employee productivity	-	Absenteeism	Training budget
2	HR score card on training	-	Split by function	-
3	Employee performance	-	Employee turnover rates	-
4	HC Return on Investment	-	Qualifications	-
5	Training undergone by individual employees	-	Salary structure	-
6	Effectiveness of Training	-	Remuneration	-
7	Training undergone	-	Split by race or ethnic origin	-
8	Identify training needs of individual employees	-	Career record	-
9	Split by age	-	Track of training expenditure against the budget	-
10	Split by gender	-	-	-

Note: Rank is based on percentages

All the items that are rated by more than 40 per cent are reported in this Table.

Table 6: Factors inhibit the measurement and reporting of human resource

	Component		
	F1	F2	F3
	Insufficient resource allocation	Lack of knowledge in HR measurement and reporting	Negative impact on organization
Organization does not allocate sufficient resources to measure and report HR	.903		
HR department deals mostly with day-to-day administrative matters	.897		
More urgent tasks absorb all of the HR department's resources	.788		
There is no return seen on the investment and effort required in the reporting of HR		.875	
There is no clear guidance in measuring and reporting HR		.825	
Line managers do not view HR measurement and reporting as important		.822	
HR information could give important insight to competitors			.820
HR information could be negatively interpreted by external stakeholders			.816
HR information could be too sensitive to report			.787
Explained variation	34.467	27.707	11.814
Eigenvalue	3.868	1.402	1.003
Cronbach's alpha	.883	.824	.829

Table 7: Factors inhibit measurement and reporting of human resource by sector

	Total sample Mean (S.D.)	Sector		t	P value
		Manufacturing Mean (S.D.)	Service Mean (S.D.)		
Organization does not allocate sufficient resources to measure and report HR	3.54 (1.15)	3.69 (1.25)	3.44 (1.09)	.586	.563
HR department deals mostly with day-to-day administrative matters	3.51 (1.31)	3.61 (1.50)	3.44 (1.19)	.352	.727
More urgent tasks absorb all of the HR department's resources	3.33 (1.21)	3.61 (1.32)	3.11 (1.11)	1.119	.273
There is no return seen on the investment and effort required in the reporting of HR	2.76 (.97)	3.16 (1.02)	2.50 (.85)	1.926	.044*
There is no clear guidance in measuring and reporting HR	2.71 (1.00)	3.15 (1.28)	2.38 (.60)	2.221	.034*
Line managers do not view HR measurement and reporting as important	2.73 (1.04)	3.07 (.95)	2.47 (1.06)	1.613	.118
HR information could give important insight to competitors	3.93 (.67)	3.76 (.72)	4.05 (.63)	-1.164	.254
HR information could be negatively interpreted by external stakeholders	3.50 (.74)	3.16 (.71)	3.75 (.68)	-2.188	.038*
HR information could be too sensitive to report	3.96 (.66)	3.66 (.65)	4.16 (.61)	-2.124	.043*

Note: * p<0.05